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Security Risk Analysis of Logistical Support Solutions for MaaS and DLT-based Mitigations

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Abstract—Mobility as a Service (MaaS) is an innovative approach that makes mobility more efficient, sustainable and seamless. In particular, through the integrated use of digital ticketing solutions within MaaS systems, transportation has become more accessible and user-friendly. However, existing cybersecurity measures for logistical support and ticketing systems lag behind the complexity of these large and interdependent ecosystems. These challenges threaten the reliability and sustainability of MaaS ecosystems, disrupting their functioning and putting the privacy of passenger data at risk. Therefore, identifying risks and providing preventive solutions is a critical necessity for the success of such systems. This study presents an overview of logistical support solutions for MaaS, with a specific focus on state-of-the-art digital ticketing technologies. It identifies key cyberthreats faced by MaaS systems through a comprehensive risk assessment and considers the role of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), especially blockchain-based ticketing, in mitigating these risks.

Index Terms—Mobility as a Service, Digital Ticketing, Cybersecurity, Blockchain, DLT

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, individuals' transport needs are changing due to urbanization, cost of living, the recent pandemic, increase in private car ownership and insurance costs, parking problems, and sustainability requirements. Smart mobility addresses these changing needs in urban environments through technology-oriented solutions. It has the potential to improve the quality of life for individuals, promote safety, and optimize the efficiency of transport networks [1].

MaaS, which is an integral component of smart mobility, plays a critical role in achieving efficiency, effectiveness and sustainability goals [2], [3]. This integrated approach offers numerous benefits both for environmental and social perspective. For example, from an environmental perspective, it fosters sustainable transport by reducing traffic congestion, air pollution, and energy consumption [4], [5], [2]. From a social standpoint, it enhances the quality of life for individuals by reducing travel time and costs, mitigating noise pollution, and enhancing travel safety [2]. In addition, it addresses certain critical issues, such as climate change and access to mobility services for an increasingly aging population. These characteristics of MaaS transform urban transport, contributing to the United Nations' efforts to create more sustainable cities under Sustainable Development Goal 11 [6], and to the goal of achieving Net Zero Emissions by 2050 [7].

MaaS is a comprehensive digital platform comprising various technologies offering optimal solutions by combining different transport modes to meet users' travel needs [8], [6], [4]. This approach enables end users to access seamless multimodal and intermodal mobility services by utilizing Internet of Things (IoT) technologies [4]. It also allows users to access both public and private mobility options, and enables transactions with bundled payment solutions [8]. Additionally, it provides real-time information and booking capabilities, offering a comprehensive view of all travel-related services [9], [5].

The MaaS ecosystem is intricate and relies on the collaboration of multiple stakeholders, where each stakeholder plays a pivotal role in the seamless operation of the system. Its key actors include MaaS providers, data providers, mobility service providers, users, technical infrastructure providers, ticketing solutions, insurance companies, and dynamic multi-service travel planners [8]. Notably, ticketing solutions are a pivotal component of MaaS ecosystems, playing a central role in transport mode integration, user experience, financial sustainability, and system security.

Ticketing systems serve not only as a means of payment, but also encompass a comprehensive structure of logistical support that includes payment systems, financial sustainability, data protection/privacy, and identity management mechanisms. Therefore, the sustainability of ticketing systems depends on the protection of all these elements [10]. Furthermore, understanding the vulnerabilities in both current public transport and MaaS-based ticketing systems is crucial for preventing future cyberattacks and ensuring the resilience of logistical infrastructures.

In recent years, cyberattacks have increasingly targeted public transportation ticketing systems. These attacks disrupt the functionality of the systems, resulting in service interruptions and financial losses. This poses serious risks to the security of the MaaS ecosystem and urges to strengthen security measures. Below are some key examples of cyberattacks on public transportation ticketing systems:

- In 2023, Estonia's national railway operator was affected by Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks. These attacks significantly affected the organization's ticketing infrastructure, disrupting ticket sales terminals at railway

stations, in-train sales systems, and digital sales platforms [11].

- In 2023, Auckland Transport in New Zealand experienced a series of cyberattacks. The attack, which utilized the Medusa ransomware, initially impacted the organization's ticketing systems, online balance platforms, and customer service centers. In addition, the attackers demanded a ransom of \$1 million in exchange for not destroying the compromised data. A subsequent DDoS attack disrupted the availability of mobile app and web-based ticketing systems [12].
- In 2024, Oahu Transit Services, operating in Honolulu, was the target of a cyberattack. As a result, the Holo digital payment infrastructure was disabled [13].
- In 2024, Transport for London (TfL) experienced a cyberattack on its online payment and ticket booking systems, which resulted in the theft of approximately 5,000 customers' bank and personal details [14].

In order to address the aforementioned cyberthreats, it is imperative to explore alternative methods that increase flexibility in ticketing systems and protect transaction integrity and passenger data. In this paper, we conduct a comprehensive risk assessment of MaaS digital ticketing systems by identifying and evaluating potential mitigation approaches. We identify vulnerabilities and critical gaps in existing MaaS digital ticketing infrastructures and propose a secure, decentralized ticketing model utilizing blockchain technology. While blockchain technology is widely recognized for its potential to improve data security and trust in digital transactions, its applicability in MaaS ticketing requires further research, and our discussion contributes towards that end.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the relevant background literature. Section III examines current digital ticketing models, highlighting their security vulnerabilities. Section IV provides a risk assessment framework for digital ticketing systems. Section V introduces Ticket Chain System, a blockchain-based solution designed to enhance security, transparency, and efficiency in MaaS ticketing and payment systems by addressing the various risks identified. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper, outlining future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Despite the important role of ticketing in MaaS ecosystems, the existing literature largely addresses cybersecurity at a system-wide level, with limited focus on ticketing-specific vulnerabilities and solutions. While some studies address security risks that indirectly affect ticketing, a detailed, ticketing-centered analysis remains largely underexplored. This section reviews the existing literature, highlighting key insights as well as critical gaps that motivate the focus of our work.

[15] provides a comprehensive survey on cybersecurity risks in Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled MaaS ecosystems, highlighting vulnerabilities such as data breaches, unauthorized access, identity theft, Denial-of-Service (DoS)/ DDoS attacks, Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attacks, fake data injection,

and financial data theft. While the study does not explicitly address ticketing, the findings on adversarial AI, data privacy risks, and regulatory challenges offer a basis for identifying threats to digital ticketing infrastructures.

[3] examines MaaS security and privacy issues through a literature review between 2014 and 2024. The paper identifies seven key security and privacy issues, i.e., data security, single-point failure risk, privacy and data sharing issues, security design flaws, insider threats, denial of service attacks, and impersonation attacks. It also identifies significant gaps in four main research areas related to privacy and data sharing, interoperability, identity management, and single intermediaries. While the research does not focus specifically on ticketing, its insights into data security, privacy and data sharing, insider threats, and DoS attacks highlight key security risks that also affect digital ticketing systems. One of the key takeaways from the paper is that blockchain is considered as a potential solution to address security concerns; yet it does not present any blockchain solution.

[16] combines a literature review with expert workshop insights to underscore the insufficient attention given to cybersecurity risks in MaaS within both academic research and real-world implementations. The study identifies that MaaS is susceptible to identity theft, phishing, and large-scale cyberattacks. Furthermore, DoS attacks are recognized as a critical risk, posing the potential for widespread disruptions across MaaS platforms. In addition to these technical vulnerabilities, the study highlights key organizational challenges, including cybersecurity capability gaps among providers, ambiguities in data ownership and algorithm governance, and regulatory compliance issues, all of which further complicate the secure and sustainable deployment of MaaS platforms.

[17] reviews the literature from 2015 to 2020 to identify and analyze the barriers and risks associated with MaaS adoption. The analysis identifies two cybersecurity risks from the user perspective, the risk of personal and payment information being compromised by malicious sources, and the risk of data breaches. These risks align with the vulnerabilities outlined in digital ticketing and payment systems, particularly under financial data theft, data breaches, and unauthorized access categories.

The study [5] highlights cybersecurity vulnerabilities in AI-driven MaaS by demonstrating how Passenger Spoofing Attacks (PSA) can manipulate travel planning systems through falsified passenger profiles, fake reservations, and fraudulent ticket requests. These findings indicate broader cybersecurity risks in digital ticketing and payment, particularly in fake data injection and manipulation, authentication weaknesses, insecure Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), tampered tickets, and service disruptions.

[18] examines the cybersecurity vulnerabilities of public transportation systems in Florida, focusing on electronic ticketing, mobile fare payment, onboard Wi-Fi, and traffic control infrastructure. The study highlights data breaches, unauthorized access, and financial risks in mobile fare payment and ticketing systems, alongside network-based attacks such

as MitM, system infiltration, and fake data injection. The study also identifies authentication weaknesses, insecure API communication, and financial fraud risks in digital ticketing. Additionally, it emphasizes cybersecurity gaps among providers and regulatory compliance challenges, advocating for stronger encryption, authentication, and system monitoring.

[19], conducted by ENISA (The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity), examines vulnerabilities across network infrastructures, operational technology, and governance structures, offering insights into how these risks impact Intelligent Public Transport (IPT) security and resilience. It covers many threats, including insider threats, hacking, DoS/DDoS attacks, identity theft, data breaches, insecure communication and data exposure, manipulation of ticket verification systems, and trojan applications. In addition, payment systems are identified as critical assets requiring protection. The study also emphasizes the need for a common European Union (EU) approach to IPT security and standardization, particularly for critical components like payment systems.

[20] conducted by the International Association for Public Transport (UITP) is a comprehensive research on ticketing systems in MaaS. However, its primary focus is exploring the role of ticketing as a key enabler for seamless multimodal transportation. The findings revealed that a trust-based approach to organizational cooperation, technical interoperability, and data sharing is essential for the success of MaaS ticketing systems. The cybersecurity aspect of the study was kept limited, where API security and data privacy were the only issues addressed. This research guided our understanding of API security risks and data-sharing concerns in ticketing system integration within MaaS.

[21] examines future security challenges in public transport through a systematic evidence-based review of academic and policy literature. The study analyzes security across five key domains: threat detection, crisis management, cybersecurity, staff training, and passenger security. It broadens cybersecurity risks, including data protection, infrastructure security, and privacy in mobile platforms; thus, it directly supports the Data Sharing and Privacy Risks and Mobile Application Risks identified in our paper.

[4] employs the STRIDE (Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information disclosure, DoS, Elevation of privilege) threat modeling framework to identify security threats within the MaaS ecosystem, including passengers, the MaaS app, transportation operators, and third-party ticketing and payment service providers, and then proposes mitigation measures. These identified threats align with the digital ticketing and payment risks in our paper, specifically mapping to insecure authentication, manipulation of ticket verification systems, fake data injection and manipulation, tampered tickets, fraud risks, data breaches and unauthorized access, and DoS attacks.

In our previous work, [22], we identified critical security risks in shared e-scooter systems, which is one of the popular micromobility methods within MaaS. Several of these risks are closely related to digital ticketing systems, particularly data breaches and privacy violations, unauthorized access and

identity theft, service disruptions and DoS attacks, and mobile application vulnerabilities. Building upon these insights and addressing the broader gaps identified in the literature, this study conducts a focused cybersecurity risk analysis for MaaS digital ticketing systems and proposes a blockchain-based mitigation framework.

III. TICKETING SYSTEMS IN MAAS

Digital ticketing systems constitute a fundamental component of MaaS, which encompasses multimodal transport networks. This section provides an overview the primary digital ticketing technologies currently deployed in MaaS systems. However, physical ticketing methods are excluded from this analysis, as our focus is exclusively on digital implementations that support MaaS integration.

Current MaaS ecosystems employ four predominant digital ticketing approaches: Account-Based Ticketing (ABT), Mobile Ticketing, Open-Loop Ticketing, and Closed-Loop Ticketing [23], [20]. Each of these approaches presents unique characteristics and security considerations that affect their suitability for MaaS integration. As shown in Table I, these different ticketing approaches are being implemented across various MaaS deployments globally, demonstrating their real-world applicability in diverse regional contexts.

A. ABT

ABT represents a cloud-centric framework where all fare calculations, payment processing, and travel rights are centrally managed via a back-office system [24]. Users can access various transport services through a single account using mobile applications, debit/credit cards, contactless EMV cards, or Near-field Communication (NFC)-enabled smart devices. Once the trip ends, the system automatically calculates the appropriate fare and deducts it from the user's account.

While ABT offers an enhanced user experience through seamless integration and flexible payment options, it also introduces notable security risks. The centralized storage of sensitive data such as payment details, travel patterns, and user preferences, presents an attractive target for cyberattacks. Furthermore, the continuous data exchange among various transport modes, stations, and payment systems increases the number of potential attack vectors, thereby amplifying system integration risks. Additionally, the complexity of integration requirements may introduce vulnerabilities in identity verification processes, posing significant challenges for user authentication. Recent implementations demonstrate that successful ABT deployment requires robust security frameworks and standardized protocols for system interoperability [25].

B. Mobile Ticketing

Mobile ticketing systems leverage the capabilities of smartphones to facilitate ticket purchase, validation, and journey initiation. In particular, these systems utilize multiple technologies such as Short Message Service (SMS), Wi-Fi/3G/4G, NFC, QR codes, bluetooth and visual validation methods. Typically, trip initiation operates through two primary models:

Check-in/Check-out (CICO) and Be-in/Be-out (BIBO). CICO requires active check-in at the beginning of the trip and active check-out at the end. With BIBO, the mobile application automatically detects the beginning and end of the trip using Bluetooth [18]. In both of these methods, the fare is then calculated based on the distance traveled.

However, despite its advantages, mobile ticketing also faces security challenges. [26] categorizes these challenges under three main headings. First is data security, which includes secure storage of user financial, personal, and travel data. Second are fraud risks, such as counterfeit ticketing, identity theft, and unauthorized access lead to revenue loss. Third are technical security challenges, include implementing secure elements in NFC technology, mobile device security, and network communication security.

In particular, QR-based and visual ticketing systems are especially prone to specific threats. QR codes, for instance, can be exploited through phishing, command injection, or other social engineering techniques [18]. Similarly, visual validation methods are vulnerable to replay attacks where an attacker captures a screenshot of a valid ticket and reuses it to bypass the verification process. This method allows unauthorized access by exploiting the static nature of visually presented tickets [18].

C. Open-Loop Ticketing

Open-loop ticketing systems enable users to pay for transit services directly using standard contactless EMV cards or mobile wallets, thus eliminating the need for transport-specific tickets. There are three types of open-loop systems: the Known Fare model, the Pre-purchase model and the Cumulative model [27].

In the Known Fare model, the fare is predetermined and charged at the time of card tap. This model is commonly applied in systems with fixed fares and usually single-boarding operation. In contrast, in the Pre-Purchase model, a specific ticket is purchased prior to travel and stored in a travel account. The system recognizes the card when the same card is used for a journey. This model is often adopted in transit systems offering monthly or annual subscription options. Furthermore, in the Cumulative model, the card is used only for authentication at the beginning of the journey and the fare is calculated at the end of the day once the travel activity is completed. This model is particularly suitable for multi-modal transport systems. For instance, the introduction of open-loop ticketing in London, as a complement to the Oyster card, has demonstrated benefits such as increased passenger numbers, reduced the cost of physical tickets and transport passes, and, most notably, improved user satisfaction [23].

Despite these benefits, open-loop systems present notable security and financial risks. One key concern is deferred authorization, which allows users to tap and board even with insufficient funds. While this mechanism is essential for ensuring fast and seamless transactions, it also exposes the system to fare evasion and settlement failures, especially when

users lack sufficient funds or deliberately exploit time gaps in transaction verification [27].

D. Closed-loop ticketing

Closed-loop ticketing systems operate on specific platforms and require users to access transport services using a smart card issued by the operator. These cards must be either preloaded with funds (i.e., a prepaid system) or linked to a subscription model. In such systems, all fare related data, travel rights and transaction records are stored directly on the card itself. Typically, these cards contain either a magnetic stripe or Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID)/NFC [18] technology. Moreover, the card is only valid within a specific city or transport network. Notable examples include Istanbulkart in Istanbul, Oyster Card in London, and Myki in Melbourne.

However, these systems present particular security vulnerabilities due to the sensitive data storage on the card itself. For example, contactless smart cards can be read from short distances without user interaction, raising concerns about unauthorized data access. A notable case in Singapore demonstrated that EZ-Link cards could be scanned remotely, allowing attackers to retrieve detailed user travel histories without physical contact [18].

In addition, some implementations' lack of strong encryption mechanisms makes these cards susceptible to cloning or manipulation. A well-known case involving The Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) students revealed vulnerabilities in the Massachusetts Bay Transportation Authority (MBTA) ticketing system. The students found that both magnetic stripe and RFID cards stored fare values locally and could be easily modified, thereby allowing unauthorized access or unlimited travel without valid payment [18].

While each digital ticketing approach offers distinct advantages in terms of user convenience and system efficiency, they also introduce various vulnerabilities that may compromise the overall integrity of MaaS ecosystems. The following section presents a detailed assessment framework to better understand and address these security concerns across digital ticketing and payment systems in MaaS.

IV. RISK ASSESSMENT IN DIGITAL TICKET AND PAYMENT SYSTEMS IN MAAS

The risk assessment framework proposed in this paper classifies threats into two categories: Digital Ticketing Risks and Payment Systems Risks, as summarized in Table II. This categorization reflects both the technical and organizational dimensions of MaaS ticketing security. Specifically, it integrates findings from a literature review conducted in Section II, practical implementation challenges reported in existing systems, and identified cybersecurity vulnerabilities in FinTech applications, particularly those related to ticketing and payment systems.

A primary security concern in digital ticketing systems is the risk to data privacy. MaaS platforms collect and process extensive user data, including personally identifiable information (PII), travel histories, and payment details. Therefore,

TABLE I
REPRESENTATIVE EXAMPLES OF TICKETING MODELS IN GLOBAL MAAS
DEPLOYMENTS

Region	MaaS Name	Mobile App	Ticketing and Payment Functions
Germany – Karlsruhe	Regiomove [28]	✓	ABT
Italy – Trento	OpenMove [29]	✓	ABT
Switzerland-Nationwide	FAIRTIQ [30]	✓	Mobile Ticketing (BIBO Model)
Brazil – Salvador	MetroBahia [31]	✓	Closed-Loop Ticketing (MIFARE, transitioning to EMV)
USA – New York	OMNY [32]	✓	Open-Loop Ticketing
Oman – Nationwide	Mwasalat [33]	✓	ABT
Italy – Campania	UNICO Campania [34]	✓	Mobile Ticketing with QR format tickets
Monaco – Nationwide	Monapass [35]	✓	Open-Loop Ticketing
USA – Portland	Hop Fastpass [36]	✓	ABT

unauthorized access or data breaches may result in severe privacy violations, such as user movement profiling or identity theft [15], [4], [19], [37], [17], [18], [21]. Notably, there is a risk that operators and platform providers may misuse user travel data for purposes like targeted marketing or revenue generation without user consent, raising significant legal and ethical issues [15], [18].

In addition to privacy risks, system security vulnerabilities expose digital ticketing systems to various threats. Network-based attacks, such as DoS/DDoS attacks, can overwhelm system resources, rendering ticketing services inaccessible [15], [3], [16], [19], [38], [37], [4]. Similarly, MitM attacks can occur [37], [38], [15], [18], particularly targeting users operating over unsecured networks, potentially leading to unauthorized ticket validation and fraudulent financial transactions. Furthermore, system infiltration threats such as hacking, Remote Code Execution (RCE) [39], Zero-Day exploits [38], and Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) [37], can compromise the integrity of ticketing infrastructures. These attacks often aim to gain unauthorized access, control system resources remotely, or exploit unknown software vulnerabilities, ultimately enabling fraudulent ticket generation and disruption of validation processes. Another critical issue is the risk to data integrity, stemming from fake data injection, data manipulation [15], [5], [4], as well as supply chain attacks [37], [38], where attackers compromise third-party service providers to infiltrate the primary systems. These risks can compromise the authenticity of ticket validation processes and undermine the overall reliability and trustworthiness of MaaS ticketing

infrastructures.

Mobile applications, essential to digital ticketing, introduce their own vulnerabilities. The first major risk is authentication and access control weaknesses [21], [4], [5], often leading to user account compromise through insecure authentication mechanisms. The second is insecure communication and data exposure [19], [21], driven by insecure Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) [18], [20], lack of encryption, and weak data transfer protocols [18], [37]. Additionally, trojan applications pose a significant threat [18], [38], [19], disguising themselves as legitimate ticketing apps to steal user credentials or payment data and perform malicious activities.

Risks associated with electronic ticketing include tampered tickets, storage vulnerabilities, service disruptions, and replay attacks. Specifically, tampered tickets involve unauthorized modification or duplication of digital tickets to gain illicit access. In addition, local value storage vulnerabilities arise from the ability to change or copy ticket values stored locally on the card, as demonstrated by the MBTA attack in closed-loop ticketing systems. Lastly, in replay attacks, attackers record legitimate ticket displays (e.g., QR codes) and replay them to gain unauthorized access without possessing a valid ticket [18].

Insider Threats constitute another critical risk area within digital ticketing systems [19], [15]. Malicious insiders such as developers, service administrators, and managers may engage in activities such as stealing or manipulating critical data, jeopardizing user privacy and system integrity. Moreover, the sale of sensitive information for financial gain can significantly elevate identity theft and fraud risks. Finally, accidental data disclosures, stemming from low security awareness or misconfigurations, also pose serious threats to user confidentiality.

Regarding payment systems, two main risk categories are identified: Financial Risks and Organizational Risks. Financial risks may arise from payment system vulnerabilities, which attackers exploit for fraud and unauthorized transactions [38], [37], [18]. Theft of financial data is particularly critical, as compromised payment credentials directly can lead to financial losses [15], [38], [37], [17], [18]. Furthermore, weaknesses in transaction verification processes may enable the authorization of illegitimate transactions [38], [18], [37], [4].

Organizational risks, meanwhile, stem from deficiencies in governance and security practices of service providers [16], [18]. Gaps in cybersecurity capabilities among providers leave systems vulnerable to attacks. Data ownership and algorithm control issues, especially in shared ticketing ecosystems, raise concerns about data misuse and breaches. Cross-border data sharing introduces additional vulnerabilities, especially when personal or transactional data is transferred across different legal jurisdictions without adequate security and compliance measures, exposing organizations to significant privacy and regulatory challenges. Finally, regulatory compliance challenges complicate fraud detection and prevention efforts, thus exacerbating security risks.

Although each risk category independently poses significant challenges, creating complex vulnerability chains within MaaS

ecosystems. For example, a successful network-based attack such as a DoS attack (System Security Risk) could disrupt real-time authentication mechanisms in a MaaS ticketing system, leading to gaps in user verification and increased data exposure (Data Sharing and Privacy Risk). This, in turn, may enable unauthorized transactions or identity theft, resulting in direct financial losses for both users and service providers (Financial Risk).

TABLE II
RISK CATEGORIES FOR DIGITAL TICKETING AND PAYMENT SYSTEMS IN MAAS

Digital Ticketing Risks	Data Sharing and Privacy Risks – Excessive Data Collection and Misuse [15], [4], [18] – Data Breaches and Unauthorized Access [15], [19], [37], [4], [17], [18], [21] – Identity Theft [15], [16], [19], [38], [37]
	System Security Risks – Network-Based Attacks (DoS/DDoS Attacks [15], [3], [16], [19], [38], [37], [3], [4] and MitM Attacks [37], [38], [15], [18]) – System Infiltration [18] (Hacking and System Crashing [19], [37], [16], RCE [39], Zero-Day Exploits [38], [37], and APTs [37]) – Data Integrity Risks (Fake Data Injection and Manipulation [15], [5], [4], and Supply Chain Attacks [37], [38])
	Mobile Application Risks – Authentication and Access Control Weaknesses [21], [4], [5] – Insecure Communication and Data Exposure [19], [21] (Insecure Transfers and APIs [18], [20], Lack of Encryption [18], [37]) – Trojan Applications [18], [38], [19]
	Electronic Ticketing Risks – Tampered Tickets [18], [4] – Local Value Storage Exploits [18] – Replay Attacks [18]
	Insider Threats – Stealing or Manipulating Critical Data [19], [15] – Selling Sensitive Information [19], [15] – Accidental Data Disclosure [19]
Payment Systems Risks	Financial Risks – Payment Systems Vulnerabilities [38], [37], [18] – Theft of Financial Data [15], [38], [37], [17], [18] – Fraud Risks [38], [18], [37], [4]
	Organizational Risks – Cybersecurity Capability Gaps Among Providers [16], [18] – Data Ownership and Algorithm Control Issues [16] – Cross-Border Data Sharing Risks [16] – Regulatory Compliance Challenges [15], [16], [18]

These interconnected risks highlight the limitations of traditional centralized ticketing architectures and emphasize the need for more robust, decentralized solutions. The following section presents our blockchain-based framework designed

to address these security challenges while maintaining the flexibility and convenience expected in modern MaaS systems.

V. A POSSIBLE SOLUTION: TICKET CHAIN SYSTEM DESIGN

A blockchain system fundamentally functions as a distributed peer-to-peer (P2P) network that employs a consensus algorithm to maintain a shared ledger across multiple distributed nodes worldwide. The key characteristics of blockchain technology are outlined as follows [40], [41], [42]:

- **Trustless Operation:** Blockchain does not require participants to develop trust between us to establish a collaboration or business. Smart contracts allow participants to decide on the processes and payments to be done automatically as the predefined processes are completed.
- **Decentralization:** Blockchain facilitates decentralized processing and management by leveraging network participants collaboratively. This eliminates the single point of failure, a major vulnerability in centralized systems. While decentralization enhances security, it introduces complexities in system design and management. Poorly implemented decentralized systems may suffer from inefficiencies such as network latency and prolonged consensus iterations.
- **Transparency:** Blockchain ensures equal access to information for all participants, fostering accountability. Transparency helps uncover hidden aspects of a system, such as undisclosed service costs, transaction routes, and associated fees.
- **Open Source:** The open-source nature of blockchain allows for continuous code review, enhancing security and integrity. Contrary to concerns, it does not inherently introduce vulnerabilities, as blockchain relies on cryptographic functions alongside mechanisms such as network size, reputation systems, and role assignments.
- **Autonomy:** Distributed consensus mechanisms enable secure data validation and appending across geographic locations, thereby enhancing process autonomy.
- **Immutability:** Blockchain ledgers follow an append-only structure, ensuring data permanence and preventing tampering. Depending on the consensus algorithm, records are appended only after achieving confirmation from 50%-66% of validators, reinforcing data integrity.
- **Anonymity:** While blockchain ensures transparency in data storage, it also preserves user anonymity by revealing only blockchain addresses rather than real-world identities. Identifying an entity typically requires extensive data collection and analysis, making de-anonymization challenging.

Thanks to its characteristics given above, blockchain technology offers significant advantages in enhancing security and resilience within MaaS ticketing and payment systems. Identified issues in Table II and how blockchain can address these risks are given below.

A. Digital Ticketing Risks

- **Data Sharing and Privacy Risks:** Trustless operation feature of blockchain removes the requirement of trust to a centralized server to not misuse the collected. Additionally, autonomy mitigates unauthorized access and data breaches due to the fact that all operations are public and predefined. Immutability of blockchain data prevents any data integrity attacks protecting data credibility. Lastly, anonymity in blockchain systems mitigates user identity theft and calibrated attacks.
- **System Security Risks:** Decentralized nature of blockchain systems mitigate the risk of DoS attacks, as the absence of a centralized entity prevents a single point of failure. On the other hand, in addition to decentralization, the autonomy feature addresses the system infiltration concerns as the system is managed by multiple entities; and in case an entity becomes unresponsive, the rest of the system continues processing. Additionally, consensus requirement for any data addition to the shared ledger prevents fake data injection attacks protecting the data integrity.
- **Mobile Application Risks:** Access and authentication rights are granted and verified by a decentralized autonomous blockchain system, therefore, related concerns are addressed. For example, encrypted communication and signed requests in blockchain systems mitigates attacks those address authentication and access rights, data exposure due to insecure communication.
- **Electronic Ticketing Risks:** Blockchain-based ticketing prevents any ticket tampering attacks as the tickets on blockchain are immutable. Additionally, ticket processing interruption, any service disruption and local value storage exploits are addressed by decentralized blockchain architecture. Even when some entities become unavailable in a blockchain system, the rest of the entities ensures system responsiveness and liveness.
- **Insider Threats:** In a blockchain system, entities' real world identities are masked due to the anonymity feature. Therefore, accidental data closure and people identity exposure are alleviated. Additionally, available encryption mechanisms supports the protections against these security concerns.

B. Payment Systems Risks

- **Financial Risks:** Theft of financial data and fraud risks are addressed by encryption mechanisms and decentralized trustless operations in blockchain. As user's identities are masked and any operation on blockchain does not requires trust from individuals, theft of financial data is not a concern.
- **Organizational Risks:** Decentralized operations prevents a single entity to own data, therefore data ownership-related cybersecurity concerns are not exist in a blockchain system.

Additionally, any vulnerability can be noticed and fixed easily due to the open source feature of blockchain systems.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study provides an overview of the digital ticketing payment methods employed in MaaS Systems and conducts a comprehensive analysis of the cybersecurity risks encountered in such platforms. After the conducted analysis, we suggest how a blockchain-based ticketing solution can address these risks.

Additionally, while this study focuses on identifying risks and proposing blockchain-based mitigation strategies, it is important to note that real-world implementation of such systems may introduce practical challenges beyond discussion given in this paper. These include integration complexity, required technical expertise, and resource constraints. Further research is needed to assess these concerns in depth.

In our future work, we will conduct further analysis to evaluate the robustness of blockchain-based ticketing systems against the cyberthreats mentioned in this paper by implementing security tests on our proposed blockchain-based MaaS, *SmartMoveChain* [43]. Our proposal introduces an entity-based chain approach and contains *TicketChain* as one of its key components, designed to process all ticketing requests via smart contracts while ensuring maintenance of the user privacy and system security.

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